

Influence of Reference and Information Services Delivery on User Satisfaction in University Libraries in Nasarawa State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated how the delivery of reference and information services influences user satisfaction in university libraries in Nasarawa State, Nigeria. The study adopted a descriptive survey design, involving 366 respondents drawn from three university libraries through proportionate stratified and simple random sampling. Data were collected using a 32-item structured questionnaire covering service types, delivery methods, service extent, factors influencing user satisfaction, challenges, and strategies for improvement. Descriptive statistics, including frequency counts, percentages, and mean scores, were used to analyse the data. Findings revealed that core reference services, such as answering user queries, bibliographic compilation, instruction, and current awareness services, were consistently delivered and significantly influenced user satisfaction, whereas specialised and digital services, including live chat, email reference, AI chatbots, and virtual access to e-resources, were underutilised. Traditional, in-person delivery methods, such as reference desk services and user orientation, were predominant, and positive staff–user interactions contributed meaningfully to satisfaction. The study also identified major challenges affecting service delivery, including inadequate user skills, limited staff assistance, poor accessibility of resources, unreliable internet, and erratic power supply. The study concludes that effective reference and information services, particularly traditional and personalised services, enhance user satisfaction, whereas digital and automated services require further development and integration. Based on the findings, the study recommends the consistent provision of both core and specialised services, the integration of digital platforms alongside traditional methods, continuous staff training, and investment in reliable infrastructure to optimise library service delivery and enhance user satisfaction.

Keywords: Reference services, Information services, User satisfaction, University libraries, Nasarawa State, Service delivery

Introduction

Universities play a pivotal role in national development by generating, preserving, and disseminating knowledge for the benefit of society, serving as the highest level of formal education. Agbe, Digitemie-Batubo, and Ode (2025) note that in Nigeria, universities are central to producing skilled manpower, fostering research, and supporting technological and socio-economic advancement. They explain that universities provide teaching, research, and community services designed to equip graduates with intellectual and practical skills to address societal challenges. Aver (2024) emphasises that universities

develop individuals' capacities to understand their environment and contribute meaningfully to national growth, highlighting that access to relevant, timely, and accurate information is essential for achieving educational and research objectives. This dependency places university libraries at the center of academic and intellectual life, making the efficiency and effectiveness of reference and information services critical for supporting teaching, learning, and research, and for promoting user satisfaction.

University libraries serve as intellectual hubs where students, lecturers, researchers, and administrative staff converge to access a wide range of information resources. Oyewole and Ajayi (2022) explain that libraries are dynamic repositories of knowledge, offering both physical and digital resources that facilitate learning and research. According to Oyewusi and Oyedoade (2019), libraries enhance institutional research culture by ensuring access to current and reliable information, while reference and information services guide users in locating, evaluating, and effectively utilising information. Sahabi and Unobe (2025) emphasise that the availability, accessibility, and relevance of these services directly influence user engagement and satisfaction, as service quality encompasses timeliness, accuracy, and responsiveness. Temboge and Ga'anda (2022) note that as universities increasingly adopt digital platforms, the delivery of reference services has expanded beyond traditional desks to include online consultations, live chat, and email support, demonstrating the growing complexity and significance of these services in shaping user experience. This evolving landscape raises important questions about how effectively university libraries in Nasarawa State meet user expectations, forming the rationale for investigating the influence of reference and information services delivery.

User satisfaction in university libraries is recognised as a key determinant of academic success and research productivity, influencing the degree to which libraries contribute to institutional educational objectives. Salah, Mommoh, and Malik (2024) note that libraries must adapt continuously to the changing needs of users, emphasising responsive, user-centred reference services. Usoro (2019) explains that reference services act as a bridge between library resources and users' informational needs, with the competence of library staff, availability of relevant resources, and efficiency of service delivery shaping satisfaction. Ubwa, Ubwa, and Agbo (2022) stress that modern university libraries must integrate both physical and digital services to ensure accessibility and engagement, while personalised services and understanding diverse user behaviours are crucial to meeting expectations. Uganneya, Ape, and Ugbajir (2014) observe that despite these advancements, challenges such as limited staffing, resource constraints, and the growing complexity of information needs persist, highlighting gaps in understanding how reference and information service delivery affects user satisfaction in Nasarawa State. Agbe, Digitemie-Batubo, and Ode (2025) further assert that examining these influences can provide empirical insights to enhance library service quality and academic support within the state.

Statement of the Problem

University libraries are established to provide high-quality reference and information services that enable students, lecturers, and researchers to access relevant information, conduct research effectively, and achieve their academic goals. When these services are delivered efficiently, users benefit from timely, accurate, and relevant information, while staff responsiveness enhances the overall library experience. However, inadequate delivery of reference and information services can lead to user dissatisfaction, reduced trust in the library, and lower patronage. In many university libraries, challenges such as limited resources, insufficient staffing, poor user-librarian interaction, and outdated information materials often hinder effective service delivery. Users who cannot obtain prompt and accurate information may experience frustration, waste valuable time searching for resources, and face reduced productivity. Additionally, ineffective reference services can limit the development of users' information literacy skills, which are essential for navigating and utilising library resources effectively.

Preliminary observations in university libraries in Nasarawa State indicate that visits by students and lecturers have remained stagnant, while instances of user frustration appear to be increasing. This suggests that the quality and effectiveness of reference and information services may not be meeting user expectations. Despite claims that services are operational, there is little empirical evidence of how these services influence user satisfaction. This study, therefore, seeks to investigate the influence of reference and information service delivery on user satisfaction in university libraries in Nasarawa State, with the aim of providing insights to improve service quality and user experience.

Objectives

The general objective of this study was to investigate the influence of the delivery of reference and information services on user satisfaction in university libraries in Nasarawa State, Nigeria.

Specifically. The specific objectives were:

1. Determine the types of references and information services delivery for user satisfaction in University libraries in Nasarawa State.
2. Determine the methods used in delivering reference and information services for user satisfaction in university libraries in Nasarawa State, Nigeria
3. Find out the extent of reference and information services delivery in university libraries in Nasarawa State, Nigeria
4. Determine challenges affecting the delivery of references and information services for user satisfaction in university libraries in Nasarawa State, Nigeria.

Fosket's Theory of Reference and Information Services (1967)

The Fosket's Theory of Reference and Information Services (1967) presents three conceptual approaches to reference service delivery: the Conservative Theory (Minimum Assistance), the Liberal Theory (Maximum Assistance), and the Moderate Theory (Balanced Assistance). These concepts collectively describe how librarians can provide different levels of help depending on user needs, institutional policies, and available resources. The Conservative Theory emphasises education and guidance over direct provision of answers, encouraging users to engage in self-help and self-education with minimal librarian intervention. In contrast, the Liberal Theory advocates maximum assistance, where librarians use every available approach and tool to help users retrieve the information they need quickly and accurately. The Moderate Theory, which blends the two extremes, represents a balanced approach that most librarians adopt, providing sufficient help while also empowering users to develop independent information-seeking skills. In relation to this study, Fosket's theory is relevant because it explains how the level and quality of assistance librarians provide influence user satisfaction. Librarians who apply an appropriate balance between guidance and direct support are more likely to meet diverse user expectations and improve access to information. By combining professional expertise with user-centred service delivery, university libraries can foster greater satisfaction, enhance research efficiency, and promote effective utilisation of reference and information resources.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework positions university libraries as central academic institutions that support teaching, learning, and research. Oyewole and Ajayi (2022) highlight that libraries serve diverse users, including undergraduates, postgraduates, lecturers, and researchers, and provide access to relevant print and digital resources aligned with curricular and research needs. Okeaghalam, Ajibili, and Achi (2020)

explain that, over time, university libraries have evolved from traditional repositories into dynamic, user-centred knowledge hubs that integrate digital resources, flexible learning spaces, and technology-driven services. Ubwa, Aghadiuno, and Ubwa (2025) note that, through collection development, provision of access, support for scholarly communication, and digital preservation, university libraries remain indispensable to academic excellence and institutional effectiveness.

Reference and information services are the core mechanisms that connect users with the information they need. Usoro (2019) explains that reference services provide personalised assistance, guiding users to locate, interpret, and use information effectively across physical and virtual platforms. Agbe, Digitemie-Batubo, and Ode (2025) note that information services extend beyond reference interactions to include the systematic dissemination of relevant, timely information that supports decision-making, problem-solving, learning, and research. Oyewusi and Oyedoade (2019) highlight that together, these services enable users to navigate complex information environments efficiently, bridging knowledge gaps and enhancing academic productivity.

User satisfaction is a key outcome of effective reference and information service delivery, shaped by accessibility, responsiveness, staff competence, resource relevance, and the overall library environment. Sahabi and Unobe (2025) argue that timely, accurate, and user-focused services, supported by appropriate infrastructure, enhance users' perceptions of library value and reliability. Temboge and Ga'anda (2022) note that challenges such as inadequate funding, insufficient skilled personnel, technological limitations, outdated resources, low service awareness, and infrastructural constraints hinder optimal service delivery. Salah, Mommoh, and Malik (2024) and Uganneya, Ape, and Ugbajir (2014) emphasise that addressing these challenges is critical to improving service quality, strengthening user satisfaction, and ensuring that university libraries continue to fulfil their roles in supporting academic and research activities. Ubwa, Ubwa, and Agbo (2022) further assert that effective reference and information service delivery directly contributes to academic success and research productivity.

Review of Related Studies

Aver (2024) investigated the relationship between digital reference services and user satisfaction in academic libraries in Benue and Nasarawa States, Nigeria, using a correlational research design. The study involved 24,741 registered users across six academic libraries, from which a sample of 385 users was selected using proportionate stratified and simple random sampling. Data were collected using a validated questionnaire with a reliability coefficient of 0.76 and were analysed using descriptive statistics and the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. The findings revealed that digital reference service availability, accessibility, and librarians' responsiveness had no significant relationship with user satisfaction, and overall, users were dissatisfied with the digital reference services provided in the studied libraries. Both studies examine how reference-related services influence user experiences in academic libraries, with a shared focus on service delivery, user needs, and satisfaction within Nigerian university settings. However, they differ in scope and methodological approach, as the earlier study used a correlational design to assess digital reference services across multiple libraries in Benue and Nasarawa States, while the present study adopts a descriptive survey design to examine a wider range of reference and information services within university libraries in Nasarawa State alone. More importantly, the present study fills key gaps left by the earlier research by going beyond digital services to include traditional reference services, contextual challenges, institutional variations, and improvement strategies, thereby providing a more comprehensive and context-specific understanding of how reference and information services influence user satisfaction.

Sahabi and Unobe (2025) investigated user satisfaction with library services at Kaduna State University using a survey research design. Data were collected through questionnaires administered to 222 respondents, of whom 194 valid responses were analysed using statistical techniques. The findings revealed strong user perceptions of the importance of positive user behaviour and attitudes, highlighting that strategies promoting respect, cooperation, and appreciation of library resources significantly improve staff–user relationships and contribute to a more satisfactory and productive library experience. Both studies focus on how library service delivery affects user satisfaction and rely on survey methods using questionnaires to capture users’ perceptions, reflecting a shared concern for service effectiveness in academic libraries. However, while the earlier study examined general library services at Kaduna State University, with an emphasis on user behaviour, attitudes, and staff–user relationships within a single institution, the present study concentrates specifically on the delivery of reference and information services and their influence on user satisfaction across three universities in Nasarawa State. The present study also differs in scope and rigour, involving a larger sample drawn from federal, state, and private universities and employing a more structured instrument to assess service types, delivery methods, challenges, and improvement strategies, thereby filling the conceptual and contextual gaps left by the previous research.

Usoro (2019) examined reference service delivery and users’ satisfaction in federal university libraries in South-South Nigeria. One objective, one research question, and one hypothesis guided the study. Data were collected via the ISDUSQ questionnaire, administered to 1,760 respondents, representing 10% of the entire population. The questionnaire was content- and face-validated. The Pearson Product-Moment Coefficient was used as the analytical tool. The null hypothesis was rejected, and the alternative accepted. The findings revealed a significant relationship between reference service delivery and users’ satisfaction in federal university libraries in South-South Nigeria. The findings further revealed that users were satisfied with the reference services. Information service enhances satisfaction. The present study aligns with earlier research in its focus on the relationship between library service delivery and user satisfaction and in its use of survey designs with validated questionnaires. However, it differs by concentrating specifically on reference and information services across federal, state, and private universities in Nasarawa State, rather than on general library services or digital reference services alone. By employing a larger, stratified sample and examining service types, delivery methods, extent, challenges, and improvement strategies, the study fills gaps left by previous works that gave limited attention to reference and information services and overlooked contextual variations among different categories of universities.

Okeaghalam, Ajibili and Achi (2020) investigated the effect of library automation services on the utilisation of information resources in Bingham University Library using a survey research design and questionnaires. The study involved 254 sampled students, with 234 valid responses analysed using frequencies and percentages. The findings revealed low awareness and utilisation of library automation services, resulting in low user satisfaction, largely due to inadequate user search skills, inefficient and non-functional computer systems, poor internet connectivity, irregular power supply, and limited access to the library website. Both the present and previous studies employ descriptive survey designs and structured questionnaires to examine the relationship between library service delivery and user satisfaction, with due attention to instrument validity and reliability. However, while earlier studies focused on general library services, automation services, or reference services within single institutions or limited contexts, the present study differs by examining reference and information service delivery across federal, state, and private universities in Nasarawa State using broader variables. The major gap in earlier studies lies in their limited treatment of reference and information services as a distinct focus, narrow exploration of service delivery methods and challenges, and restricted institutional coverage, all of which the present study addresses through a more comprehensive and context-specific analysis.

Agbe, Digitemie-Batubo and Ode (2025) examined the influence of reference and information services on service delivery in academic libraries in Benue State using a survey research design. The study covered five academic institutions with a large and diverse population, from which 397 respondents were sampled using a scientific formula. Data collected via a validated and reliable questionnaire were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings showed that institutional repositories, thesis and dissertation databases, and bibliographic instruction were frequently used, whereas subject-specific databases, online catalogues, email reference, and interlibrary loan services were underutilised due to low awareness and accessibility challenges. Overall, the study highlighted the significant role of information services, particularly information literacy programmes and electronic databases, in enhancing users' academic experience. The present study, like previous research, uses a descriptive survey design and structured questionnaires to examine the relationship between library service delivery and user satisfaction, emphasising validated instruments and statistical analysis to capture user experiences. Unlike earlier studies that focused on limited service types or individual institutions in Benue and South-South Nigeria, this study investigates reference and information services across federal, state, and private universities in Nasarawa State, considering service types, delivery methods, extent, challenges, and improvement strategies. By addressing gaps in prior research, such as limited attention to service delivery methods, user challenges, and university ownership differences, the study provides a comprehensive assessment of how both digital and traditional reference and information services influence user satisfaction in Nasarawa State university libraries.

Research Methodology

The study used a descriptive survey design to examine reference and information services delivery and user satisfaction in three university libraries in Nasarawa State. A total population of 4,289 registered library users was considered, with a sample of 366 selected through proportionate stratified and simple random sampling to ensure representativeness. Data were collected using a structured 32-item questionnaire (USRISDQ) covering six areas: types of services, delivery methods, extent of service, influence on user satisfaction, challenges, and strategies for improvement. Both dichotomous and Likert-type scales were used, and trained research assistants helped administer the questionnaire to ensure a high response rate. Data analysis involved descriptive statistics to answer research questions. Responses were interpreted using a 2.50 mean benchmark and percentage classifications for service availability and delivery. This methodology provided a systematic and reliable approach to assess reference and information services and their impact on user satisfaction in Nasarawa State University libraries.

Results and Discussion

This section is concerned with data presentation, analysis, interpretation and discussion of findings. The presentation follows the sequence of the research question answered and hypotheses tested.

Table 1: Size Distribution and Return Rate

S/N	Institution	Population	Sample Size	Return Frequency	Return %
1	Federal University Lafia	2,819	241	233	96.68%
2	Nasarawa State University, Keffi	1,070	91	87	95.60%
3	Bingham University, Karu	400	34	34	100%
	Total	4,289	366	354	96.72%

Table 1 presents the distribution of the sample size and the corresponding return rates across the three universities under study in Nasarawa State, Nigeria. The proportional allocation technique ensured that each institution received a sample size that reflected its share of the total population of 4,289 students. Out of the 366 questionnaires administered, 354 were successfully retrieved, representing an overall response rate of 96.72%. This rate exceeds the standard benchmark commonly regarded as acceptable in social science research and indicates a high level of participation among the respondents across the institutions.

Cluster A: The types of references and information services delivery for user satisfaction in University libraries in Nasarawa State

Table 2: Frequency Counts and Percentages of the Types of References and Information Services Delivery in University Libraries in Nasarawa State

S/N	Reference and Information Services	N	D (Freq)	(%)	ND (Freq)	(%)	Decision
1	Answering user queries	354	334	94.35%	20	5.65%	D
2	Instruction services	354	254	71.750%	100	28.25%	D
3	A Compilation of bibliographies	354	300	84.75%	54	15.25%	D
4	Current awareness service	354	332	93.79%	22	6.21%	D
5	Referral services	354	354	100.00%	0	0.00%	D
6	User education services	354	284	80.23%	70	19.77%	D
7	Reservation services	354	200	56.50%	154	43.50%	D
8	Inter-library loan services	354	231	65.25%	123	34.75%	D

The results from Table 2 indicate that most reference and information services are actively delivered across the three university libraries in Nasarawa State, with referral services at 100%, answering user queries at 94.35%, and current awareness services at 93.79% showing particularly high delivery. Other services, including instruction services (71.75%), compilation of bibliographies (84.75%), user education (80.23%), reservation services (56.50%), and interlibrary loans (65.25%), are provided but less consistently. These findings partially align with Usoro (2019), who noted that effective reference service delivery enhances user satisfaction, but diverge from Aver (2024), who found no significant link between digital reference services and satisfaction in Benue and Nasarawa States. Underutilization of some services echoes Agbe et al. (2025), highlighting low awareness and access challenges, while the importance of user attitudes and staff–user interactions emphasized by Sahabi and Unobe (2025) suggests that service delivery alone does not guarantee satisfaction. Overall, enhancing utilization, accessibility, and complementary strategies such as awareness campaigns and user education is essential to optimize the impact of reference and information services.

Cluster B: The methods used in delivering reference and information services for user satisfaction in university libraries in Nasarawa State

Table 3: Frequency Counts and Percentages of the Methods of Delivering References and Information Services Delivery in University Libraries in Nasarawa State

S/N	Methods	N	MU (Freq)	(%)	MNU (Freq)	(%)	Dec
1	Library reference desk services	354	256	72.32%	98	27.68%	DM
2	In-person user orientation	354	316	89.27%	38	10.73%	DM

3	Printed user guides and pathfinders	354	354	100.00%	0	0.00%	DM
4	Readers' advisory service	354	200	56.50%	154	43.50%	DM
5	Book exhibition and display	354	256	72.32%	98	27.68%	DM
6	Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC)	354	124	35.03%	230	64.97%	DM
7	Library websites and portals	354	200	56.50%	154	43.50%	DM

Key: N = Sample (Copies Retrieved), MU = Method Used, MNU = Method Not Used

The results in Table 3 show that reference and information services in Nasarawa State university libraries are predominantly delivered through traditional, in-person methods. Printed user guides and pathfinders were utilized by 100% of respondents, in-person user orientation by 89.27%, and library reference desk services by 72.32%, while readers' advisory services and book exhibitions were used by 56.50% and 72.32% of respondents, respectively. In contrast, digital methods such as the Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC) and library websites were less frequently used, with only 35.03% and 56.50% engagement, respectively. These findings partially support Usoro (2019) and Agbe et al. (2025), who emphasized that effective service delivery through accessible and visible channels enhances user satisfaction. However, the low utilization of online tools reflects the observations of Aver (2024) and Okeaghalam et al. (2020), who reported dissatisfaction due to poor digital accessibility, limited user skills, and technological constraints. Additionally, the strong reliance on interpersonal methods, such as in-person orientation and staff interaction, aligns with Sahabi and Unobe (2025), highlighting that positive user-librarian engagement significantly contributes to user satisfaction. Overall, while traditional delivery methods remain central in Nasarawa State libraries, the limited adoption of digital platforms indicates an opportunity to enhance service delivery and optimize user experiences through improved technological integration.

Cluster C: The extent of reference and information services delivery in university libraries in Nasarawa State, Nigeria

Table 4: Mean and Standard Deviation of the extent to which reference and information services are delivered in university libraries in Nasarawa State

S/No	Extent of Delivery	N	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Answering user queries	354	2.68	0.93	High Extent
2	Instruction services	354	2.56	0.81	High Extent
3	A Compilation of bibliographies	354	2.73	0.81	High Extent
4	Current awareness service	354	2.52	0.80	High Extent
5	Referral services	354	2.23	0.91	Low Extent
6	User education services	354	2.37	1.01	Low Extent
7	Reservation services	354	2.24	0.84	Low Extent
8	Inter-library loan services	354	2.37	0.79	Low Extent
Cluster Mean			2.46	0.87	Low Extent

The results in Table 4 on reference and information services in Nasarawa State University libraries show varied levels of delivery. Core services such as answering user queries (2.68), instruction (2.56), bibliographies (2.73), and current awareness (2.52) are delivered to a high extent, whereas referral (2.23),

user education (2.37), reservation (2.24), and inter-library loans (2.37) are delivered to a low extent. The overall cluster mean of 2.46 indicates that, on average, service delivery is low. These findings align with Usoro (2019), which reports that effective core services enhance satisfaction, but they also reflect the concerns of Aver (2024), Okeaghalam et al. (2020), and Agbe et al. (2025) about underutilisation and accessibility challenges. The results also highlight the importance of staff-user interactions, supporting Sahabi and Unobe (2025). Overall, while basic reference services are adequately provided, specialised and digital services require strengthening to improve user satisfaction.

Cluster D: The extent to which references and information services influence users’ satisfaction in university libraries in Nasarawa State, Nigeria

Table 5: Mean and Standard Deviation of how references and information services influence user satisfaction in university libraries in Nasarawa State

S/No	Influence on Satisfaction	N	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Reference services provide quick and reliable responses to user inquiries.	354	2.70	0.80	Agree
2	Availability of reference services 24/7 enhances user satisfaction.	354	2.66	0.79	Agree
3	Use of live chat services improves user engagement with the library	354	2.33	0.88	Disagree
4	Reference services ensure timely access to academic resources.	354	2.61	0.83	Agree
5	Email reference services provide adequate support for complex queries.	354	2.43	0.87	Disagree
6	Integration of AI chatbots into virtual services improves response efficiency.	354	2.21	1.02	Disagree
7	Virtual services offer seamless access to e-books and digital journals.	354	2.34	0.84	Disagree
8	Reference services support collaborative academic research effectively.	354	2.67	0.87	Agree
Cluster Mean			2.49		

The results in Table 5 show that traditional, personalised reference services in Nasarawa State university libraries, such as quick responses to enquiries (2.70), 24/7 availability (2.66), timely access to resources (2.61), and support for collaborative research (2.67), positively influence user satisfaction. In contrast, digital and virtual services, including live chat (2.33), email reference (2.43), AI chatbots (2.21), and access to e-books and journals (2.34), have limited impact. The overall cluster mean of 2.49 indicates a moderate influence of reference services on satisfaction. These findings align with Usoro (2019) and Sahabi & Unobe (2025) on the importance of effective traditional services and staff–user engagement, while reflecting concerns from Aver (2024), Okeaghalam et al. (2020), and Agbe et al. (2025) about underutilisation and technological constraints. Overall, user satisfaction is driven mainly by traditional reference services, highlighting the need to improve awareness, infrastructure, and digital service integration.

Cluster E: Challenges affecting references and information services delivery for users’ satisfaction in university libraries in Nasarawa State, Nigeria

Table 6: Mean and Standard Deviation of the problems of references and information services delivery for user's satisfaction in university libraries in Nasarawa State

S/No	Influence on Satisfaction	N	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Unavailability of current and up-to-date research materials.	354	2.86	1.00	Agree
2	Difficulty in locating relevant materials for academic assignments	354	2.78	0.89	Agree
3	Inadequate user knowledge on how to access and utilise reference materials	354	2.74	1.02	Agree
4	Limited skills in using the library catalogue effectively	354	2.91	0.91	Agree
5	Poor accessibility of some library resources	354	2.85	0.93	Agree
6	Non-functional or insufficient internet facilities within the library	354	3.21	0.82	Agree
7	Erratic power supply is hindering the effective use of internet-based services	354	3.34	0.81	Agree
8	Inadequate assistance provided by reference staff to library users	354	2.67	0.81	Agree
	Cluster Mean		2.97		

The results in Table 6 indicate that users in Nasarawa State university libraries reported several challenges affecting reference and information service delivery. Major problems include the unavailability of up-to-date research materials (2.86), difficulty locating relevant resources (2.78), inadequate user skills (2.74–2.91), poor accessibility of library resources (2.85), insufficient internet facilities (3.21), erratic power supply (3.34), and limited assistance from reference staff (2.67). The overall cluster mean of 2.97 indicates that these issues significantly constrain service delivery and user satisfaction. These findings align with Aver (2024), Okeaghalam et al. (2020), and Agbe et al. (2025), who highlighted infrastructural, technological, and awareness-related barriers, while underscoring the importance of effective services and staff support, as noted by Usoro (2019) and Sahabi & Unobe (2025). Overall, both human and infrastructural factors are critical determinants of the effectiveness of reference and information services in these libraries.

Conclusion

The study revealed that reference and information services in Nasarawa State University libraries play a significant role in shaping user satisfaction. Core services such as answering queries, instruction, bibliographies, and current awareness effectively support users, while specialised and digital services remain underutilised. Traditional, personalised services were found to positively impact user satisfaction, whereas digital and automated services had limited influence. Several challenges, including inadequate user skills, limited staff support, poor accessibility of resources, and infrastructural constraints, hindered optimal service delivery.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made based on the findings from the study

1. To improve the types of services delivered, libraries should ensure consistent provision of both core and specialised services, emphasising user education and research support.

2. For methods of service delivery, libraries should integrate digital platforms alongside traditional in-person services to enhance accessibility and engagement.
3. To strengthen the extent of service delivery, continuous staff training and performance monitoring should be implemented.
4. To overcome challenges affecting service delivery, universities should invest in reliable infrastructure, upgraded resources, and responsive staff support to enhance overall user satisfaction.

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